

WAYS AND METHODS OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: In this article, based on the letter of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2022 No. 02/35-30/05-49, effective methods and ways of independent education of students, functions of the process of independent learning activities are presented.

Key words: Independent education, control and self-control, didactic theory, BKMK, function, credit-module system, higher education.

Currently, the organization of Independent Education of students in higher education institutions of the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 30, 2022 02/35- 30/05-49-it is carried out on the basis of the “educational instruction on the organization and control of Independent Education of students in the credit-module system in higher educational institutions”[1].

The institutions of higher education in our country provide the necessary opportunities for independent education of students. In independent education, the student himself is intended to independently use electronic and printed literature, magazines, internet educational resources, information and educational environment of the educational institution, Information and educational and methodological complexes.

In the process of completing independent educational assignments, students are directed to preliminary research activities, in which motivation for scientific research Awakens. For example, in the working curriculum of General pedagogical science, a plan of independent educational assignments is given, which is intended to direct students to additional, independent research and conduct scientific activities, which is introduced and presented to students in the introductory lesson.

The effective organization of Independent Education of students is directly related to the correct orientation, Organization of their independent activities. Student independent activities can be organized as follows:

1. Learning new learning material.
2. Processing BKMS, development of competence.

3. Implementation of control and self-control – for monitoring.
4. Coughing to perform laboratory and practical work.
5. Compilation and analysis of models in the conditions of Virtual laboratories.
6. Preparation of synopsis, abstract, project, etc.for the creation of the results of their personal –products in educational activities.
7. Preparing a lecture.
8. Preparation for intellectual tournaments, Olympiads and Concours.
9. It is necessary to provide guidance and guidance for scientific research work [2]. The preparation of students for independent educational activities can be formulated as follows: in the process of Independent Education of the student, that is, the implementation of independent educational and cognitive activities, it is advisable to carry out the following functions:
 1. Functional is a function of practical orientation.
 2. Cognitive-cognitive function.
 3. Monitoring-reflexive-control-reflexive function.

In the process of independent education, when an axiological approach or a function of value orientation is implemented, students are observed to compose, independently think, reflect, as a result of which they study the heritage of our ancestors, scientifically understand being, analyze the place and significance of material and spiritual wealth, determine values (human interest, gene pool, Homeland, language, traditions, spirituality, culture), as well as national and universal values, discover, self-esteem. On this basis, he occupies scientific-theoretical Bcoms in his specialty, professional competence is formed, and in the future, as a result of organizing his activities on the path of prosperity of the motherland, establishing his place and position in society by himself, he becomes a competent, intelligent person in every possible way. After all, in the opinion of John Dewey, “the most valuable period for a person is a period when democracy is fully won in society, a wide path is opened to the progress of Science, and many members of society become mature intellectuals”. Therefore, the student assimilates the content of value throughout his life, especially during his practical activities in the process of Independent Education, realizes the essence of human, professional values.

In didactic theory, the concept of knowledge is explained in the following two different meanings: A) the knowledge that learners must acquire; B) the knowledge acquired by them and applied in the process of practical activity, which has become personal experience. Knowledge is strengthened in the

process of activity, therefore, it is necessary to educate students the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. Knowledge that has no application in practice will soon be forgotten [3]. In the process of Independent Education, the student is engaged in a certain type of activity in the specialty of his choice. At this stage of the system of Continuing Education, an active approach is systematically organized. For example, students studying in pedagogical higher educational institutions study in educational areas of their choice, as well as mastering scientific and theoretical knowledge in both specialty and specialty disciplines, as well as preparing subjects for the type of professional activity. Strengthens them during practical and laboratory training, transforms them into skills, forms qualifications, applying them directly to their activities in the period of educational practice, qualification practice. This is done as a result of the student's independent education and activities, as a result of which their level of training for professional activities increases.

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